

Radio in the context of global information space: peculiarities and functions

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Abstract: If we take as an example of the world, nowadays, radio is gaining popularity as a tool that embodies the process of comprehensive renewal. In particular, radio was used to be just a headset, today it also includes the press, television and the internet.

As well as, listening to radio broadcasts, the modern listener has the opportunity to watch online on TV, as well as read the news on a special website of the radio.

Various experts in the description of the media can be seen expressing their views on whether the audience of the radio is declining or increasing in terms of time.

The article provides a scientific overview of the processes, news, problems in radio journalism, as well as comparing the views of scientists and experts in the field, future arrangements and recommendations.

Keywords: radio channel; information software; radio program; youth; information; news; information space; journalistic skills; broadcast; audience; globalization

While the number of information spaces in the world is growing and globalization is taking place, the media play an important role in conveying to the public the purpose, mission, content and essence of this development. Radio, which is an important form of media, has its own audience with its speed, popularity, and convenience. In particular, the radio, like other media, is still one of the leaders in the rapid delivery of the practical results of reforms in all areas of our country to the audience. Realizing this, the President and the government pay special attention to freedom of the media, speech and press. It should be noted that radio, which is a type of media, also plays an important role in the production of broadcasts on various topics.

As well as, it is known that since the invention of the radio miracle in the world, its main task is to deliver news and messages to listeners. It can be said that radio and newspapers have more opportunities to deliver news to the public faster than television. The most modern radio centers in the world are gaining the attention of listeners by delivering information at the time of the incident or just a few minutes later.

In 2010, there were about 44,000 radio stations in the world¹ but, today we can notice that their number has doubled compared to these figures. This is due to the fact that the development of modern technologies has created conditions for the creation of online radio channels, as well as traditional radio channels.

¹ Source: The World Factbook, 2010. Central Intelligence Agency, USA
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Numerous radio stations offer their listeners musical and advertising blocks in a variety of styles and directions in order to seriously follow the news, develop intelligence, logical thinking and fill the consciousness of people, and have a serious impact on the world around them through the formed imagination. about it. Radio informs the audience with its popularity, breadth and ease of reception, saturates people with new knowledge and gives specific comments. Radio also plays an important role in the complete ethical and aesthetic portrayal of a person.

Radio broadcasting has a psychological effect on the listener due to its unique, unrepeatable sound and directs information to the auditory, sound reception. Radio relies on the full imagination of the individual. He is able to control the mind with emotions. While the inconspicuousness of broadcasting is considered a disadvantage, it also has a positive side. We can say that radio makes a person think, imagine and think to the end. Therefore, these features of radio broadcasting are very important in comparison with television.

The term "radio" and its invention covers several eras around the world, and the scientist went down in history with the inventions of inventors in various directions. "Radio" – means (lat. Radiare, radio - means "to emit", "to emit light"). It also means wireless transmission and reception of information over long distances using radio waves (electromagnetic waves). The term "radio" was first coined in 1873 (almost 20 years before the invention of radio) by the English physicist and chemist William Crookes, who conducted several chemical experiments. Crookes himself did not experiment with the transmission and reception of electromagnetic waves using technology, another interesting aspect was that he was a science fiction writer. He wrote an article "Contactless Communication Between the Heads of People" and published it in one of the magazines. In an article entitled "Some Possibilities of Getting Electricity," published in one of the leading British magazines in 1892, he also used the word "radio" to describe an image receiving device. His other articles also use the words "range", "perception", and "discovery"².

Radio affects the emotions and mood of people through live sound. It is this sound that distinguishes radio from other media.

For example, radio played an important role in delivering the fastest news to the public during the war. Due to the war, the activities of district, city and district newspapers were very limited. The radio also tried to replace them. The amount of information in the radio program has been increased.

For example: During the war Yuri Levitan speech as "Moscow Speaks!"-"Говорить Москва!" made everyone serious. Levitan joined All-Union Radio" (Всесоюзного радио) in 1931. Speaker's phrase touched the hearts of many listeners. Why did all the people listen carefully to Levitan?

He attracted the attention of the audience with his serious reading of each text, fluency of speech.

As well as, during the World War II and the war which was named later as the Cold War that began around the world, further connected people with radio. During great disasters, people became close to radios and loudspeakers. Every day, people's attention was immersed to the loudspeakers installed in rural tea houses, markets, and train stations. Every hour they waited for new messages from the front. New programs were broadcast on the radio, such as "Letter to the Front" and "Letter from the Front". In the Letter to the Front, letters from parents, brothers, sisters and son-in-law were read to the children of soldiers who died on the battlefield. In the program "Letter from the Front", letters from soldiers fighting for the freedom of the Motherland to their compatriots were read on the radio. If such broadcasts raise the spirits of warriors at the front, like a mountain, and induce them to win, they will give strength and inspiration to women, old people and children who work day and night at the front, for the sake of victory.

From the above information, we can conclude that the radio soon found its listeners. This was due to the following factors:

² See: www.wikipedia.org.

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First, during the war years, regular broadcasting was carried out through loudspeakers installed in sheds and fields;

Second, listeners will also be able to listen to various songs and programs through small radios installed in their homes;

Thirdly, it attracted the attention of people and the fact that the programs were conducted by representatives of speaker and art, famous poets and writers with their unique sonorous voices.

In fact, the greatest magical power of radio is that it is associated with sound, and everyone prefers to listen to those who are pleasant to the ear, soft in their place, serious in their place, cheerful in their place.

Radio, as an exceptional, verbal-oriented type of press, confidently entered human life and took its rightful place in it. With the advent of radio, people began to hear the news of social life more quickly, became more aware of the world, and at the same time broadened the horizons of social thinking.

With its appearance and features, the radio posed the following problems to experts in the field:

a) since the invention of radio, along with the press, it has played an important role in delivering the most important messages to the people, requiring further improvement from year to year as it relates to radio technology;

b) with the advent of radio, the art of speech of mankind has further improved, so that the delivery of the most important news, messages to people in a unique way;

c) faster and better delivery of information to the public through the introduction of scientific and technological advances and new technologies;

g) there is a need to inform people about the most important events and happenings in society as soon as possible.

“Radio is a type of media based on a specific electronic technique. Radio is not a product of the press in the original sense, i.e. it does not reproduce the word by print, but reproduces it by means of special instruments. In this respect, radio is a separate type of media based on technology. Radio has a special place in the classification of media. That is, seeing newspapers and magazines reaches the human mind through reading printed words, while radio affects them by hearing sound. This is due to man’s most ancient and natural ability to receive information through the ear, which is the most basic sense organ. In this sense, it can be said to be a continuation of the art of oral discourse, heraldry, rhetoric that served as it did before the press came into being, in other words, a technically repetitive view of the above means.³”

The definition which was given to radio summarizes the simplest and most straightforward, understandable ideas. Originally created by physicists to transmit sound over long distances, radio has come a long way to this day.

As a result of the development of telecommunications, radio did not lose its audience, but increased it due to the rapid use of data and the popularity of programs. Broadcasting is formed according to the principle of time, differs by program. To this day, the tone, simplicity, and at the same time, the emotionality of the live speech allows radio listeners to enjoy constant gratitude.

The era of globalization has also had an impact on traditional radio activities. The development of the Internet, first of all, led to the creation of electronic versions of analog radio stations. The first online radio, Internet Talk Radio, began operations in the United States in 1993 and soon gained a worldwide audience. In Russia in 1996, "Europe Plus", "Serebryany dojd", "Radio 101" soon rose to the top of the rankings⁴.

In Uzbekistan, online radio has also emerged as an online version of modern radio. The first online radio in the country, Sharqona, was established on December 9, 2007 by Global Media Group.

³ Hamdamov Yu. Audiovisual journalism. J. - T., 6-vol. NMIU “Uzbekistan”, 2019. P.131-132.

⁴ <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>.

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Professor Y.A. Zasursky emphasizes the importance of technological factors that contribute to the development of radio: "Mass communication today is manifested in many radio broadcasts. It has gained new opportunities due to the development of satellite communications and the Internet, and has penetrated practically all fronts. With the help of the Internet, you can listen to radio in different and distant countries. The development of satellite and digital broadcasting will ensure the effective organization of radio stations in different parts of the world".⁵

The development of information technology has affected the activities of radio, as well as many other areas. Now listeners are accustomed to listening to radio broadcasts through car radios or mobile phones. Although radio and television were created with a history of almost a century, they retained their fans, and with the advent of the internet, they gradually began to lose their listeners. The reason was that the global network was able to cover not only the press, but also television and radio, newspaper sites.

If we take as an example of the world, nowadays, the radio represents a comprehensive renewal process. In particular, while previously radio was only a headset, today its virtual version combines the features of the press, television and the Internet. In addition to listening to the news on the radio, the listener has the opportunity to watch online on TV and read the news on a special website of the radio. This means that radio should increase its audience and listeners by creating a healthy competitive environment among other media, not only provide them with information, but also provide them with spiritual and enlightenment education, public opinion formation, recreation, is sought to perform a number of functions such as giving aesthetic pleasure.

Although radio, a form of mass media, was invented much later than the press, it soon gained its own audience.

It only took 20-30 years, not 300 years, like the press, for radio to take its place in the hearts of its listeners with its loud, unique, juicy voice. Scientists conducting research on radio theory try to prove the reason for this through various opinions and arguments.

V.V.Voroshilov in his book "Journalism" mentions as: "Radio has a truly unique set of features ... People listen to the radio while doing other things, and at the same time about all the events - news, entertainment programs, theater and will have detailed information about the market. Unlike newspapers and magazines, radio enters our home from the scene of an incident with the resounding voice of an obvious person who is able to transmit information at the time of the incident. The radio then allows you to record the data on a magnetic tape for reuse when the reliable facts of your favorite programs are needed. In the conditions of advanced telecommunications, radio did not lose its listeners, but also managed to increase the number of listeners due to the speed of data transmission, the popularity of programs. Radio broadcasting is formed according to the principle of time, stratified by programs. The universality, simplicity and, at the same time, the effectiveness of the live speech make it possible to ensure the stability of the listeners' loyalty to the radio to this day."⁶

In fact, radio has found its listeners in its time by not choosing a place and a specific time compared to other media, press and television. Another important aspect was to directly affect people's emotions through sound, music, song, to encourage them to think, to think, to reflect.

The invention of radio also led to the creation of an important type of journalism. Radio journalism has become an important and integral part of the media.

"Radio journalism is the main form of human professional and information-communicative activity, i.e. the transmission of audio production (broadcasting) to a distance and its reception by the recipient (listener). The main tool of radio journalism that converts sound into production is the means of radio communication. Radio journalism is a unique environment based on human socio-professional activity, consisting of technical means and natural sound expression (speech, noise, music), which are considered to be the capabilities of radio. Radio journalism is a type of audio

⁵ Zasursky Ya.N. The most open source of information // TV and radio broadcast: history and modernity / ed. Ya.N. Zasursky. M.: Aspect Press, 2005; P. 146.

⁶ Voroshilov V.V. Journalism. SPb: Publishing house of Mikhailov V.A., 2000.P.51.

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activity, as a result, it is a generalization of radio broadcasts or broadcasts that have a psychological, emotional impact on the audience.”⁷

These comments of the Russian scientist are a simple and detailed view of the definition given to the science of radio journalism. Radio journalism is a type of auditory activity that directly delivers a radio product (broadcast) prepared by a journalist to the listener.

M. Minkov's definition of radio journalism is also explained very clear. “Radio journalism is a type of journalistic activity based on the use of technical means in radio broadcasting. Radio journalism also appears as a complex of broadcasting and is a product of the creative activity of journalists”⁸.

A radio journalist is a person with a professional background who specializes in radio broadcasting and has a special knowledge of the ability to write targeted texts. Systematic perception of the environment around us and the separation of voices, the development of sound, the unification of oral speech in a way that is understandable to oneself and those around oneself is a great feature of human activity.

It is precisely the sound waves (sounds) that are the means of speech expression that separate man from the animal in the biological world. Praising the capabilities of the human brain and psyche, man feels like a thinking, conscious being because of his ability to produce, understand, and process (process) the complex set of sounds of the world around us.

Radio journalism is one of the most complex social phenomena, a field of radio, which is a means of creating and disseminating mass media, relying on the extraordinary technical capabilities of radio. Radio journalism has not always stood by the press, television, cinema, news agencies, but began to work with them in solidarity, partnership and consensus.

“Radio journalism, as a type of journalistic activity, is characterized by the effective and high-speed delivery of current information in a short period of time. Radio journalism also affects listeners through the intermediate of sound.”⁹

It should be noted that, it's hard to find someone who doesn't know any radio station intimately, even if it's not a favorite. As V.V.Smirnov noted, radio “introduces us to different people. The broadcast informs about a lot of useful information in the preface, expands our worldview, gives tips. We listen to music and entertainment broadcasts on various radio channels, focusing on breaking news, analyzing events based on the opinion of an expert in the field. You can always find programs of any taste, interest and passion on the air.”¹⁰

D.Sh.Abdulina and L.M.Podolskaya-Katchan's article titled: "Problems of modern radio broadcasting"¹¹ reveals the current issues facing the modern broadcasting industry, emphasizing that this requires both long-term and systemic solutions. Therefore, these issues can be resolved in the next few years.

“The most important task of radio is to inform the public about important events and happenings in society. It also plays a key role in speed. Broadcasting is one of the most important features of radio, as it provides the public with news that is not covered in other traditional media.”¹²

This means that reporting is the main function of radio, which transmits important messages that take place in the country and abroad. Today, the entertainment and leisure function of radio is also important, and through the airwaves, listeners not only receive information, but also listen to entertainment broadcasts, music and songs.

⁷ Klyuev, Yu. V. Radio journalism: the basics of the profession: textbook. allowance / Yu. V. Klyuev. St. Petersburg State University, 2015. P.12.

⁸ Minkov M. On the problem of genres in radio broadcasting abroad. M., 2013, p. 46

⁹ Methodological problems of studying television and radio broadcasting. - M., 2011, p. 27

¹⁰ Smirnov, V. V. Forms of broadcasting: functions, typology, structure of radio programs / V. V. Smirnov. M.: Aspect Press, 2002. P.11.

¹¹ Abdulina D.Sh., Podolskaya-Katchan L.M. Problems of modern radio broadcasting // Young scientist. No. 13 (147). March 2017

¹² Karimov A., Qosimova N., Ismoilova K. et al. Audiovisual journalism. J.– T., vol. NMIU “Uzbekistan”, 2019. P.130. Philosophical Readings XIII.4 (2021), pp. 2547-2555. 2551

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The task of radio is to broadcast and distribute important events in the country and the world. On the radio, a reporter, editor, commentator, and translator-editor prepare news. The speaker and the presenter convey this information to the listener. It should be noted that the presenter of the program - announcer, presenter or journalist is required to have a comprehensive knowledge. Because the listener learns the important, current news of the day through them. Confidence in information arises through them. Finally, the phrase "radio news is written primarily for the ear" is often repeated in the words of experts.

Indeed, people listen to the radio. So, when writing for radio, first of all, we choose simple and clear-sounding words that our ears can quickly perceive and are often used in speech. The sentences are also short and brief."¹³

From today's point of view, a reporter preparing radio material is at the same time a journalist, a presenter, a speaker. The reason is that a journalist is quick to deliver a message and news to the audience, on the one hand, and on the other hand, he tries to "find" important aspects of the event in an interesting way, feeling exactly what he saw.

Now let's talk about the role of young people as representatives of the radio's active audience.

Youth are the most active and progressive layer in any country. So, as a media observer in general, young people are always at the forefront. In addition, the issue of youth is one of the most topical and important issues covered by the media today. Unlike the press, the Internet, and television, how does radio play a broad role in covering youth issues? What percentage of the radio channel's audience is young?

In order to find answers to these questions, we conducted a telephone survey among 18-70-year-old fans of the "Youth" radio channel.

The survey included the following questions:

1. Do you listen to radio broadcasts?
2. What is the purpose of listening to the radio?
3. When do you find time to listen to the radio, does listening to the radio interfere with your work?
4. Which radio show are you a fan?
5. Do you think that radio channels have become a means of entertainment?
6. What topics would you like the radio channels to cover?
7. What radio programs do you like and what projects do you dislike?
8. How do you assess the difference between the activities of public and private radio channels?
9. What suggestions do you have about the activities of radio channels?

According to the survey results, 70 out of 100 people said they listen to radio broadcasts.

Most of the listeners listen to the radio for relaxation and listening to music — 60 people.

Housewives, car drivers listen during the day - 50 people.

Congratulations program, informational programs, various fun quizzes and games - 60 people.

Radio channels are a means of listening to music for middle-aged people, and a means of recreation and news for the older generation.

According to the responses of 30 people who regularly listen to the radio, long conversations make listeners tired. The combination of short, concise, interesting news and music-songs does not bore the listeners.

Today young people cannot imagine their lives without music. No matter what they do during the day, they at least listen to music and songs that are transmitted over the radio through their cell phone headphones.

The Russian Center for Public Opinion Research (VTSIOM) published on its website on February 19, 2019, "Radio: We Love but Don't Listen?" in a headline article presented the results of a study on whether Russians listen to radio.

¹³ Saidov H., Tokhlieva N. Reporting skills. Study guide. T.: Gafur Gulyam Publishing House, 2008, P.65.

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The share of radio listeners has declined significantly over the past 10 years: if in 2009 two-thirds of Russians (63 percent) listened to radio, today the share of listeners is 48 percent. Every second respondent (50 percent) does not listen to the radio at all, and this share is high among 18-24 year olds - 69 percent¹⁴.

It should be noted that a number of factors can be attributed to the decline in radio listening among 18-24 year olds. Comparing the data obtained over the past 10 years, it can be concluded that the number of users of non-radio media, in particular the Internet, has increased. Today, the Internet reflects all the media. This does not mean that no one listened to the radio. The main issue is to increase the number of listeners of the radio, which is the object of our study, in particular, to expand the coverage of young people.

Consistent with a telephone survey conducted to determine the audience of radio channels in the country, the majority of the population prefers to listen to music (74%) and news (53%) on the radio, usually in private vehicles (56%) and at home (41%). Scientific and educational programs (28 percent) and "talk" genre programs (24 percent) are of less interest to radio listeners. Music is mostly listened to by 25-34 year olds (88 percent) and older people (64 percent among those over 60). For 45-59 year olds, academic and curriculum programs are more interesting (36 percent).

According to the FDF group marketing agency, which studied the musical preferences of Muscovites at the request of Russia's First Game TV channel, "97 percent of respondents between the ages of 16 and 25 (half of them students) said they listen to music every day. The average young person spends 4 hours a day on music. More than a third of respondents (37 percent) listen to music for one to three hours a day (see Table 1), 27 percent for 3 to 5 hours, and another third (30 percent) for more than 5 hours. Only 6 percent of respondents listen to music for less than an hour a day.¹⁵" From this it can be concluded that a large part of the youth audience listens to the radio mainly for music and song. The reason is that today's youth do not have the patience to listen to long lectures, conversations and dialogues. They only hear short news and news happening in the republic and abroad.

The agency also asked respondents in a survey, "Do you usually listen to music ...?" Do you listen to music often ...? He also asked questions such as: For respondents, listening to the radio for more than 5 hours a day is a very common pastime. This is due to the fact that most players and mobile phones have a radio function, which means you can listen to music everywhere - on the street, in traffic, in a fitness club, or even in a lecture at an institute. It includes radio fans as well as, drivers who spend a lot of time in traffic jams from work and work.

Certainly, depending on the cultural and other characteristics of each country, the main time on the radio may be different in different countries, but most listeners listen to the radio during the day from 08.00 to 14.00. If we divide the airtime into conditional intervals, we can divide the time interval when the radio is listened to on a large or small scale. Examples can be seen in the six-day interval between the republic and the regions:

Table 1. Radio listening times

A certain part of the day	Listening time
Early morning	06:00-08:00
The main time of the Morning	08:00-10:00
The main time of the Day	10:00-15:00
Daytime	15:00-18:00
The main time of the evening	18:00-20:00

¹⁴ <https://wciom.ru/index.php?id=236&uid=9560>

¹⁵ <https://www.sostav.ru/news/2011/06/22/soc2/>

Night time	20:00-06:00
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The maximum radio listening time during the day is indicated in bold in the table: this is the main time of the morning - from 08.00 to 10.00, the main time of the day - from 10.00 to 15.00 and the main time of the evening - from 18.00 to 20.00.

If we compare the time spent listening to the radio and watching TV, according to the average daily coverage, the radio audience during the day outperforms the television audience.

U.S. researchers conducted a series of experiments to identify psychographic segments of listeners on radio stations, depending on the time of listening. Table 2 shows which segments of radio listeners listen to the radio at what time.¹⁶

Table 2. Dividing the audience into a specific type of listening

Listening Time	Audience / Segment
Morning and afternoon	Housewives
In the evening	Young people
Afternoon at the weekends	Sportsmen
Sunday morning	Tourists
Between 20.00 pm	Workers
At night	Transport workers

As it can be seen from Table 2, housewives listen to the radio in the morning and in the afternoon. Evening time is most acceptable among small audiences. People who work at certain times of the night listen to the radio. Obviously, the division into segments is done randomly, but this division gives an idea of the radio broadcasts of different social groups.

It is also important to note that a particular place or condition is less important for listeners when listening to the radio. The reason is that you need a comfortable place to watch TV. Usually, during the day, the radio is listened to in different places: at home, at work, in transport, in places of rest. The radio signal is also received from different carriers: it can be a home or work radio receiver, a car radio, a small individual radio receiver. In recent times, radio has been frequently placed on various mobile devices such as MP-3 players, mobile phones, as well as distributed over the Internet.

To monitor and research a radio audience, most countries around the world use a diary panel - a survey in which respondents indicate which radio station they are listening to and at what time. Unfortunately, this form of data registration has several drawbacks. For example, it is difficult to correct the exact time and name of the radio frequency in a vehicle or other public place where the respondent is an involuntary radio listener. Therefore, experts understand the need to change the existing methods of recording radio listening.

Originally invented to transferring sound from a certain distance to another remote area, radio has had an impact on the development of many industries over its long 100-year history. That is:

- made a huge contribution to the development of technology;
 - used as a political force in the state intelligence service;
 - serves as a bridge in international relations;
 - As a type of media, it serves to provide timely information to the public;
 - provides spiritual and educational education to the population, especially the younger generation;
 - Leads in the formation of public opinion, advanced advocacy in protecting the minds of young people from various destructive ideas;

¹⁶ <http://www.advlab.ru/articles/article614.htm>

- has become a close companion for people with disabilities, especially the blind;
- The radio also broadcasts live theatrical performances and expands the audience;
- Developed a new form of reading - the promotion of radio reading through the project "Radio Book";
- Radio has become a valuable legal, socio-economic, medical and cultural, in short, a valuable tool for advising and guiding listeners in various spheres of society;
- the radio updated its actions in various formats. For instance, "Avtohamroh" radio acts as a bridge between drivers, pedestrians and traffic police officers, while "Nostalgia" radio broadcasts world classical music and songs.

Another aspect, while the invention of radio was another major contribution to the development of technology, on the other hand, it became an important means of conveying information to the public. Compared to the direct press, it has expanded its audience by being quick, not choosing a specific time and place to receive information, attracting the listener's attention through a resounding, unique voice, influencing their emotions, and encouraging them to think.

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